

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

OPPORTUNITIES TO INCREASE THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This article discusses the possibilities of increasing the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises. In order to increase the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises, the enterprise's labor productivity, return on investment, profitability and production volume were analyzed, and the volume of products produced, the number of employees and fixed assets at the enterprise were analyzed by correlation and regression. Based on the results, proposals and recommendations were developed.

Keywords: economic efficiency, textile industry enterprises, labor productivity, return on investment, profitability, production volume, fixed assets.

1. Introduction

Currently, many textile industry enterprises face a number of problems in achieving economic efficiency. This article identifies and explores opportunities for improving the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises. Labor productivity, return on investment, profitability, and production volume were studied to improve the economic efficiency of textile enterprises.

Economic efficiency indicates the economic result of production. For example, the result of product production, management, the introduction of new equipment and technology, improving the quality of work, etc. Economic efficiency is characterized by the amount achieved due to saving materials, labor, money and other resources, saving time, reducing construction times, saving labor costs, reducing waste of working time, accelerating the turnover of funds, increasing the volume of product production, improving the quality of work and other results.[1]

Labor productivity plays an important role in assessing the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises. Labor productivity is the ability of human labor to produce a greater or lesser amount of output in a given period of time.[2]

At the same time, it is an urgent problem to analyze in detail the many indicators and factors that affect the possibilities of increasing the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises.

2. Literature Review

Many scientists and researchers have conducted research on increasing economic efficiency in industrial enterprises and reflected this in their scientific works.

Klaus Schwab, a German economist, says in his book "The Fourth Industrial Revolution" that "technology provides the high efficiency that many people desire".[3]

Romana Rauter, an Austrian economist, has conducted several scientific studies on economic efficiency in her research. In her work, she expressed the following thoughts on economic efficiency: "The increasing number of products and services, the rapid change in market demands are trends that require manufacturing

companies to introduce new practices to remain competitive. Information search and its integration in the context of open innovation are practices that can lead to increased success. This practice contributes to the achievement of economic efficiency of the enterprise. However, the full range of potential open innovation partners has not yet been sufficiently studied, and their impact on innovation efficiency remains unclear. We investigated the role of different open innovation partners in increasing economic innovation efficiency and sustainable innovation efficiency".[4]

Savitskaya Glafira Vikentievna, an economist, has reviewed several studies on economic efficiency in her research. "Efficiency is a complex economic category, and a wide range of different indicators are usually used to measure its level. All efficiency indicators in their economic content express the ratio of results to costs or resources".[5]

Gulyamov Saidakhror, an economist, also touched on economic efficiency in his research "Cloud technologies: economic efficiency, mobility, no need for your own infrastructure, low cost of technical maintenance".[6]

Based on the definitions given by economists above, efficiency is a specific result achieved by an enterprise over a certain period of time, and it is worth noting that modern economists often associate the term "efficiency" with competitiveness, optimality, effectiveness, productivity, and profitability.

3. Research Methodology

In this study, in order to improve the economic efficiency of textile enterprises, indicators that evaluate the economic efficiency of the enterprise and the factors affecting these indicators were studied. Also, a correlation and regression analysis model of factors affecting the production volume in "Asakatekstil" Joint Stock Company was developed.

4. Results

In this study, we have identified indicators and factors that affect economic efficiency in order to improve the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises. We can see the identified indicators and factors in the table below.

Table 1

Indicators and factors influencing economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises			
Economic efficiency			
labor productivity	Return on investment	Profitability	Production volume
Staff qualification level	Number of equipment	Raw material quantity and price	Raw material supply
Working conditions	Equipment operating hours	Production process efficiency	Production technology
Motivation	Market conditions	Energy and resource use	Labor force and skills
Work organization	Management quality	Product range and design	Financial situation and investments
Control	Foreign trade	Financial management and cost control	Market and demand

According to this table, the indicators that have a high impact on the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises are labor productivity, return on assets, profitability and production volume, and the factors that have a high impact on these indicators.

The volume of production, number of employees, and fixed assets of "Asakatekstil" Joint Stock Company in 2015-2024 were analyzed, and based on the results of the analysis, the level of correlation was determined in the table below.

Table 2

The degree of correlation of factors affecting the volume of production in the "Asakatekstil" Joint Stock Company

	Y	X1	X2
Y	1		
X1	0,951355	1	
X2	0,921162	0,934068	1

In this table, we can see that the number of employees and fixed assets are highly dependent on production volume, and that the number of employees and fixed assets are also highly dependent on each other.

$$Y=13,53+0,26X1+0,03X2$$

Regression analysis model of indicators in "Asakatekstil" Joint Stock Company

In the above model, we can see the regression analysis of the indicators of the "Asakatekstil" joint-stock company.

5. Conclusion and suggestions.

Based on the results of the research conducted and conducted on the possibilities of increasing economic efficiency in textile industry enterprises, the following conclusions, proposals and recommendations were developed:

✚ It is necessary to improve labor productivity in a textile industry enterprise. To do this, it is necessary to regularly improve the skills of employees.

✚ Return on investment is also essential for increasing economic efficiency. Therefore, it is necessary to upgrade the existing equipment to modern ones.

✚ Profitability is also one of the best ways to increase economic efficiency. By improving the quality of raw materials and increasing the variety of products, the economic efficiency of an enterprise can be increased.

✚ Production volume is a great opportunity to increase the economic efficiency of an enterprise, in which raw material supply, production technology, labor force, and skills play a major role.

Through the above suggestions and recommendations, there will be opportunities to increase the economic efficiency of textile industry enterprises.

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